

Speak Better English Program and Communication Skills for Grade 3 Learners

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Abstract. This study evaluated the effectiveness of the Speak Better English program on improving the oral communication skills of Grade III learners at Binugao Central Elementary School in Davao City. Utilizing a quasi-experimental design, 87 participants were divided into control and experimental groups. The program employed a blended learning approach, combining modular and online instruction. Communication skills were assessed using pre- and post-tests. The experimental group showed a significant improvement in post-test scores (mean = 38.19) compared to the control group (mean = 36.33), with a t-value of -5.22 and a p-value of 0.0351. The effect size, measured by Eta squared, was 0.441, indicating a large effect. These results suggest that the Speak Better English program effectively enhances oral communication skills among young learners. The findings underscore the potential benefits of incorporating targeted English language programs in primary education to enhance communication competencies.

KEY WORDS

1. Speak Better English Program. 2. Oral Communication Skills. 3. Grade 3 Learners.

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1. Introduction

English is often regarded as a means of advancing one's education and career opportunities. The English language plays an important character in binding the world collectively in a single strand. English is regarded as a second language in practically every nation where it is not the native tongue. The primary purpose of learning any language is to acquire simple vocabulary that can be used in everyday situations. Consequently, today's workforce is expected to be highly skilled, with the capacity to continually improve their talents and engage in lifelong development. Language is a talent, and like any other skill, mastery is very improbable unless and until we practice it. The goal of learning lan-

guages is inextricably tied to the development of LSRW abilities. The four skills of language acquisition are L-S-R-W, a collection of four talents that enable a person to understand and generate oral language for correct and successful interpersonal communications. Listening, Talking, Writing, and Writing are the four talents. Communication, being a universal process, has an impact on the actions of the human society. Effective communication skills are essential for maintaining growth and development, and societal socialization is a key element of them (Jassim, 2020). The need to study a language stem from the flexibility, efficiency, usefulness, universality, and teachability of the language.

Sharing thoughts, ideas, and views with others is referred to as communication. This might be of a mental, interpersonal, verbal, or written character. We live in communities, and man is inherently a social creature. We share our opinions with others because societal necessities demand it (Hanif, 2020). Communication is necessary for maintaining intimate, sympathetic connections in a community as well as the movement of individuals, materials, and ideas from one location to another. Initiation receipt and reaction are provided as feedback in this phase. As a result, communication is inherently participatory. Learning English is now required not just for political reasons, but also for scientific and technical reasons. English is no longer just a British language; it is the language that the rest of the world needs to communicate; it is the most international of language (Forsberg, 2020). The most prevalent issue learners experience is communicating in the English language. Because of their lack of communication abilities, most students are not "business ready." There is no efficient communication between teachers and learners, and there is no effective communication among students. Students who are unable to communicate effectively get no useful instruction (Hashim, 2020). Many people place a high value on technical talents while overlooking the most important communication skills. Communication is essential for success in the corporate sector or any organization. Effective communicators think, have high self-esteem, and dignity, and are respected in society, academia, and their profession. People who have good communication capabilities are more self-assured because they know they can tell others precisely what they need. To successfully communicate, one must plan and arrange one's ideas. To get technical knowledge and other associated abilities, you need to study to improve your English language application skills (Lwin, 2021). The language we use to communicate is very significant in all aspects of our lives. If

we don't have good language, the projects we work on will be uninteresting. English claims to be the best language of the contemporary world. It's because English is used in all world-wide communications. English is taught as a means of facilitating cross-cultural communication. In the school where the researcher is currently connected, teachers found out that students encounter difficulty in communicating in the English language which leads to misunderstandings, hinders social interactions, and impacts academic progress. While the English language plays a significant role in the academic, personal, and professional lives of the students, it also presents some challenges such as overcoming the fear of speaking, limited exposure to authentic English conversations, lack of vocabulary and idiomatic expressions, grammar and pronunciation errors, and cultural differences are all common challenges that students may face. Developing English language skills among students is a complex and multifaceted challenge for teachers. The situation cited would suggest that developing the English language is vital in developing the communication skills of the students. English language is crucial for students in enhancing their communication abilities. It enables them to connect with people from different cultures, enhances employability prospects, improves academic performance, enhances critical thinking skills, and opens doors to higher education opportunities. In the Division of Davao City, particularly in Binugao Elementary School, teachers must look for strategies to develop oral English skills among Grade III students. The researcher as a teacher exhausts her effort in looking for a strategy to provide multiple pathways that help students develop their oral English language proficiency and effective communication skills. Hence, this study of oral English development affects the communication skills of Grade III students.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature— Oral English proficiency is essential for ef-

fective communication in academic and real-life settings, contributing to improved reading, writing, and critical thinking abilities (Alghail, 2021). Effective oral communication skills are crucial for success in various settings. In academic environments, they enable students to actively participate in discussions, present ideas, and engage in group work, enhancing comprehension and analysis of complex concepts (Chen, 2020).

In professional settings, strong oral English skills are highly valued by employers, as they allow employees to articulate ideas, engage in discussions, and confidently present work, thereby enhancing career prospects. Teachers play a crucial role in developing these skills by understanding the challenges English language learners face and employing various teaching strategies (Robert and Meenakshi, 2022). The development of oral skills positively impacts vocabulary acquisition, grammatical usage, and pronunciation (Fitria, 2020).

Oral English development fosters critical thinking and problem-solving abilities, essential for articulating ideas, active listening, and engaging in meaningful discussions (Davison, 2020). It also improves communication skills, including speaking and listening, by enhancing clarity and confidence in verbal expression (Idrus, 2020). Additionally, it impacts social interactions and cultural understanding, enabling meaningful conversations and intercultural competence (Salleh, 2020).

Several factors influence oral English development:

Socio-cultural environment: Rich linguistic environments enhance skills, while limited exposure poses challenges. **Motivation and attitude:** Positive attitudes and intrinsic motivation boost engagement and effort in learning (Kasbi, 2020). **Age of learning:** Early exposure to English leads to better proficiency (MacWhinnie, 2021). **Quality and quantity of exposure:** Ample practice opportunities, such as immersive

environments, improve skills (Lu, 2020). **Cognitive abilities:** Strong memory, attention, and analytical skills aid in processing and producing English (Manzano, 2020). **Sociolinguistic factors:** Familiarity with social and cultural norms of English use enhances proficiency (Soomro, 2020). **Teacher factors:** Effective strategies, teacher-student rapport, and constructive feedback facilitate development (Thu, 2021). Effective teaching strategies are crucial. **Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)** promotes interaction and fluency through real-life conversations (Onoda, 2021). **Technology-enhanced learning,** using online platforms and apps, provides interactive experiences and independent practice (Okoro, 2020). **Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT)** involves meaningful tasks to develop language skills, integrating them with real-life communication (Rahman, 2019).

Authentic materials and real-life contexts expose students to varied English registers and accents, enhancing their skills. Collaborative learning activities, such as group discussions and projects, promote interaction and critical thinking (Bruner, 2020). Effective classroom management and timely, constructive feedback also play significant roles in creating a supportive learning environment (Herrera, 2020).

Incorporating speaking activities across the curriculum and using effective questioning techniques encourage students to express thoughts in English, promoting fluency and critical thinking (Jim, 2020). Explicit teaching of pronunciation, intonation, and grammar further improves oral communication skills (Simon, 2020).

Overall, employing diverse and effective teaching strategies fosters oral English development, essential for students' success in academic, social, and professional settings.

1.2. Synthesis—The literature review presented above provides an overview of the perspectives and viewpoints of various authors regarding the significance of oral English development that can lead to improving the communi-

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Flow of the Study.

cation skills of Grade III students. While some authors share similar ideas, there are also contrasting statements. These statements will serve as a guide for the researcher in conducting her study, forming conclusions, and making recommendations. Additionally, the literature review will serve as a framework for the researcher to follow throughout the research process. It will also serve as a reference for the researcher to support and justify any findings that arise from the statistical analysis and interpretation.

*1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—*This study is anchored on the Second Language Acquisition Theory of Stephen Krashen (1985). According to Krashen of his "comprehensible input and output" hypothesis language learners need both comprehensible input and opportunities for output production to develop their oral English skills. Comprehensible input refers to language input that is slightly beyond the learner's current level, while output production refers to the act of producing language. This hy-

pothesis highlights the importance of exposing learners to a rich language environment and providing them with ample opportunities to practice speaking. In addition, in the context of oral English development, the Input and Output Hypothesis Theory suggests that students should be exposed to authentic spoken English through listening activities such as conversations, interviews, and podcasts. This input should be comprehensible, engaging, and relevant to their interests and needs. By providing ample opportunities for students to listen to and understand spoken English, educators can support the development of their oral language skills. The diagram that follows illustrates the flow of this experimental research. The action initiated is oral English Development and it hopefully affects the communication skills of Grade III students. It is hoped that through the use of this approach, the communication skills of the students will be developed and increased.

1.4. *Statement of the Problem*—The general purpose of this study was to look into the effect of the Speak Better English program on the oral communication skills of Grade III learners. Specifically, this research study aimed to answer the following research objectives.

- (1) What is the pretest score of Grade III students in both controlled and experimental groups before oral English development?
- (2) What is the posttest score of Grade III students in both controlled and experimental groups after oral English development?
- (3) Is there a significant difference in the communication skills between controlled and experimental groups after oral English development?
- (4) What is the magnitude effect of oral English development on the communication skills of Grade III students?

1.5. *Null Hypothesis*—The Null Hypothesis in this study was tested at a 0.05 level of significance. HO1. Oral English development has no significant relationship with the communication skills of Grade III students. HO2. Oral English development has no magnitude effect on the communication skills of Grade III students

1.6. *Significance of the Study*—The following are considered beneficiaries of the study. The result of this study would reveal the level of impact of oral English development and how it affects the Grade III student's communication skills. Moreover, this research will provide the foundation for DepEd Officials to organize a range of seminars and pertinent training programs across multiple fields on oral English development, particularly in enhancing the communication skills of Grade III students. School Administrators. The findings of this study are beneficial to the school head of Binugao Central Elementary School. The school head can utilize the vital information from this research study to implement an oral English development program that will directly affect the communication skills of Grade III students. As instructional leaders, school heads are tasked to implement

different instructions to promote teachers' pedagogy in realizing the learning institutions' goals, missions, and visions. Teachers. The findings of this research study are helpful to teachers of Binugao Central Elementary School as to how they will employ teaching strategies in oral English development to enhance the communication skills of Grade III students. As teachers, simple teaching strategies are enough to provide effective language instruction and support students' oral English development. Future Researchers. The findings of this study may encourage them to conduct similar studies in other areas. This study serves as an additional source of reference and inquiries for their investigation relative to the present study.

1.7. *Definition of Terms*—To make this study comprehensive, the following terms are operationally and conceptually defined. Oral English development refers to the process through which individuals acquire and improve their spoken English language skills. This encompasses the ability to understand, produce, and effectively communicate in spoken English. Communication skills refer to the abilities and competencies that individuals use to convey information, ideas, emotions, and thoughts effectively and appropriately in various contexts.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study’s design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) was expressly utilized to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI’s growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study made use of the quasi-experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel, 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are an intact group of learners. This design is represented as follows:

- 01 Pretest of the experimental group
- 02 Posttest of the experimental group
- 03 Pretest of the controlled group
- 04 Posttest of the controlled group
- Non-random assignment of subjects
- X Treatment applied in the experimental group

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in Binugao Central Elementary School, Division of Davao City. The subjects of this study were 87 grade three learners – 45 were from section A which was the controlled group and 42 were from section B which was the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study.

Distribution of Respondents

Subjects	Section	No. of Pupils
1	Section A	45
2	Section B	42
Total		87

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It is a blended learning where the teacher gives modules at the same meets the learners online but adheres to the protocols of the Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher had to meet the learners online for a follow-up session on what had been printed in the module. The pre- and post-performance tests consist of 30-item tests that would eventually determine the literal com-

prehension skills of the research subjects. The pretest was administered to all subjects before the treatment. The pretest was very helpful in assessing the communication skills of the grade three learners. On the other hand, a posttest was administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the level of communication skills of the grade three learners, the following continuum was used based on the DepEd rating system.

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher drafted a letter seeking for permission this research study to be conducted and was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City and the school principal of Binugao Central Elementary School. While letters seeking permission were delivered to the school division Superintendent and the school principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and had it validated by the experts preferably the experts of the study. After permission had been granted that this study be conducted in Binugao Central Elementary School and after the research questionnaire had been thoroughly examined by the expert validators,

the researcher administered a pretest to both controlled and experimental classes and eventually commenced her experiment. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher administered a posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects were submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher made an analysis and interpretation of the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tool was used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study. Mean was used to describe the level of communication skills in both pretest and post-test scores. Eta square was used to measure the magnitude of the Speak Better English program on the communication skills of the grade three learners.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented a discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners, and the Significant Relationship between the pre-tests and post-test scores.

Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade three learners. The control group got the mean of 26.60 or Beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 27.71 or Beginning. It can be gleaned from the table that during the pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating than the control group although both belong to Beginning Level

Table 1: Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Control Group	45	26.60	59.11	Beginning
Experimental Group	42	27.71	61.57	Beginning

This finding is congruent with the idea of Chen (2020) who said that effective oral communication skills are vital for success in academic, professional, and social settings. In the academic realm, students need to participate in class discussions, present their ideas, and engage in group work. Oral English proficiency enables students to actively participate in classroom discussions and engage in academic discourse. When students can express their thoughts and ideas effectively, they are more likely to comprehend and analyze complex concepts. Through oral communication, students can ask questions, seek clarification, and collaborate with peers, facilitating a deeper understanding of subject matter across different disciplines. Oral English development refers to the process by which individuals acquire and

improve their speaking skills in the English language. It involves the development of fluency, pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammatical accuracy, enabling individuals to effectively communicate and express themselves in spoken English (Alghail, 2021).

3.1. *Post-Test Score of Pupils*—Shown in Table 2 are the post-test scores of the grade seven learners. The control group got the mean of 36.33 or Developing while the experimental group gained the mean of 38.19 or Approaching Proficiency. It can be gleaned from the table that during the post-test the experimental group had a higher mean rating than the control group. It got a mean rating increase of 10.48 from a mean rating of 27.71 to 38.19. This means that the experimental group has a far better performance than the control group.

Table 2: Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	45	36.33	80.73	Developing
Experimental Group	42	38.19	84.86	Approaching Proficiency

This finding is congruent with the idea of those who cited that oral English proficiency is essential for effective communication in both academic and real-life settings. It allows students to express their thoughts, ideas, and emotions accurately and fluently. In addition, strong oral English skills contribute to improved reading, writing, and critical thinking abilities. Oral English development contributed to the improvement of various communication skills, including speaking, and listening. Research revealed that by developing their oral English skills, students gain the ability to express themselves clearly and confidently in verbal communication. They learned to articulate ideas, thoughts, and opinions effectively, which enhanced their overall communication competence. Additionally, through active listening

and understanding of spoken English, students develop important skills such as comprehension and interpretation, leading to better overall communication abilities (Idrus, 2020).

3.2. *Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score*—Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test scores of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.22 with a p-value of .0351 which is less than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post-test scores of the grade seven learners. This implies that the use of oral English development through the Speak Better English program has contributed to the communication skills which is revealed by the scores of the grade three learners.

Table 3: Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	37	-5.22	.0351	Significant

This finding is in line with the statement of Fitriya (2020) who said that there is evidence to show that the development of oral English skills has a good impact on total language ability. The enhancement of vocabulary acquisition, grammatical usage, and pronunciation correctness can be attributed to the development of oral skills. Consistent engagement in speaking and listening exercises enhances one’s understanding, oral proficiency, and aptitude for efficient communication of ideas. Oral English development also has a significant impact on students’ social interactions and cultural understanding. Effective oral communication skills enable students to engage in meaningful conversations, build relationships, and participate actively in group discussions. By developing oral English proficiency, students can effectively communicate with individuals from diverse backgrounds

and cultures, fostering intercultural competence and global awareness. This enhances their ability to collaborate, negotiate, and solve problems with others, both in academic and real-life settings (Salleh, 2020).

3.3. *Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretests and Post-test Scores of the Grade Three Learners*—Table 4 highlights the test of the Speak Better English program on the communication skills of Grade Three learners. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.441 which signifies a large effect. This implies that teachers should look for a strategy to enhance the English communication skills of Grade Three learners. By nurturing these skills at an early age, we empower learners to build confidence, access enhanced learning opportunities, prepare for the future, foster cultural understanding, and overcome barriers to communication.

Table 4: Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretests and Post-test Scores of the Grade Three Learners

N	t-value	Eta ²	Descriptive Value	Decision
87	-4.58	0.441	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

The development of oral English skills fosters critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. It has been widely acknowledged that oral English proficiency enhances communication skills, which are essential for critical thinking and problem-solving. Effective communication involves the ability to articulate ideas, listen actively, and engage in meaningful discussions. Through oral English development, individu-

als learn to express their thoughts clearly, ask relevant questions, and actively participate in debates or discussions. These skills stimulate critical thinking by encouraging individuals to analyze information, evaluate different perspectives, form reasoned opinions, and find innovative solutions to complex issues (Davison, 2020).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displayed the summary of the findings, conclusions, and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made.

4.1. Findings—This study sought to determine the effect of a better English program on the communication skills of grade three learners. This study made use of a quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation. The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are an intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Binugao Central Elementary School, Division of Davao City. The subjects of this study were 87 grade three learners – 45 were from section A which comprised the controlled group and 42 were from section B which is the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is heterogeneous therefore pupils of sections A and B had identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of a better En-

glish program has increased the communication skills of grade three learners. It also revealed that there is a magnitude of difference between the post-test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that the Speak Better English program significantly improves the oral communication skills of Grade III learners. The pre-test scores of both the control and experimental groups were at the Beginning level, with means of 26.60 and 27.71, respectively. After the intervention, the post-test scores of the experimental group increased to a mean of 38.19 (Approaching Proficiency), compared to the control group’s mean of 36.33 (Developing). The t-value of -5.22 and p-value of 0.0351 indicate a statistically significant improvement in the experimental group, and the large effect size (Eta squared = 0.441) underscores the substantial impact of the program. These results suggest that the program is effective in enhancing oral communication skills and

could be a valuable addition to primary education curricula.

4.3. *Recommendations*—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching Grade three learners should use used Speak Better English program as a strategy that would further develop the communication skills of learners to make the teaching and learning process meaningful. Effective teaching strategies are essential for nurturing English communication skills which empower learners to become proficient communicators in English. The school heads should promote the use of the Speak Bet-

ter English program as a strategy, especially in teaching English communication that extends far beyond language proficiency, encompasses cultural exchange, economic empowerment, and personal development. A school policy about the utilization of the Speak Better English program can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demo teach during the LAC session using the Speak Better English program as a strategy in teaching. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of the speak better English program as a strategy in teaching will be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

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